

for laboratory facilities. One of the authors (R.S.S.) is grateful to Y. D. Post-graduate College, Lakhimpur-Kheri for granting leave and to U.G.C., New Delhi for the award of Teacher Fellowship.

References

1. R. H. KHAN and S. C. BAHTEL, *Agric. Biol. Chem.*, 1976, 40, 2481.
2. L. GIAMMANO, *Ann. Chim.*, 1961, 55, 175 (*Chem. Abstr.*, 1961, 55, 18725).
3. S. ALKIRA and L. MASUMI, *Yakugaku Zasshi*, 1965, 85, 418 (*Chem. Abstr.*, 1965, 63, 5640).
4. R. B. PATHAK and S. C. BAHTEL, *J. Antibact. Antifung. Agents*, 1981, 9, 9.
5. S. BAHADUR, A. K. GOEL and R. S. VARMA, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1975, 52, 843.
6. K. SASAJIMA, K. ONO, H. NAKAO, I. MARAYAMA, S. KATAYAMA, S. INABA and H. YAMAMOTO, *Ger. Offen.*, 2536164/1976 (*Chem. Abstr.*, 1976, 84, 164631).
7. L. CONTI, *Boll. Sci. Fac. Chim. Ind. Bologna*, 1964, 22, 13 (*Chem. Abstr.*, 1964, 61, 4253).
8. NG. PH. BUU-HOI and N. D. XUONG, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1953, 386.
9. J. G. HORSFALL, *Bot. Rev.*, 1945, 11, 257.

Synthesis and Mercuration of Some New 2-Arylimino-4-oxazolidones as Pesticides

J. P. NATH and D. N. ROUT

Department of Chemistry, Bhadrak College, Bhadrak-756 100 and

S. C. SATRUSALLYA*, B. K. PATTNAYAK and

G. N. MAHAPATRA

Department of Chemistry, Ravenshaw College, Cuttack-753 003

Manuscript received 29 March 1983, revised 13 February 1984, accepted 3 May 1984

CHEMISTRY¹ and wide range of pharmacological²⁻⁴ properties of oxazolidones have been cited in the literature. In the present work an attempt has been made to synthesise some new 2-arylimino-4-oxazolidones (Ia and Ib) by condensing different monoaryl ureas with chloroacetic acid and α -chloropropionic acid separately in presence of anhydrous sodium acetate in absolute ethanol medium.

Structure Ia of the compound has been established from the characteristic ir peaks at 1560 (N—C—O), 3260 (NH) and 1742 cm⁻¹ (C=O five membered β -lactum ring⁵), and pmr peaks at τ 5.8 (2H, s), 5.2 (1H, br, s) and 2.6 (4H, s) due to —CH₂— at 5-position of the ring, —NH—, and aromatic protons, respectively. Structure Ib was confirmed from ir peaks at 1560 (N—C—O), 3260 (NH) and 1742 cm⁻¹ (C=O), and pmr peaks at τ 5.6 (1H, s), 8.2 (3H, m), 5.2 (1H, br, m) and 2.6 (4H, s) assigned to —CH— at 5-position of the

ring, CH₃— at C₅ position, —NH— and aromatic protons, respectively with tetramethylsilane as internal standard. It was further substantiated from the reported⁶ sulphur analogue, 2-arylimino-4-thiazolidones under the similar experimental condition.

Further, Ia and Ib were mercurated by one equivalent of mercuric acetate with a view to enhance their pesticidal activity. Acetoxymercuri group usually enters into the *para* position⁷ of *N*-phenyl nucleus if it is free, otherwise occupies the *ortho* position of the same nucleus. The position of acetoxymercuri group is further justified from the fact that 2-imino-4-oxazolidone synthesised from urea and chloroacetic acid is never mercurated under these experimental conditions. The final evidence for the position of acetoxymercuri group comes from the following observations.

Monoacetoxymercuri compound, IIa was treated with sodium perbromide to yield compound IIIa, which was identical with 2-(*p*-bromophenyl)-imino-4-oxazolidone synthesised independently from *p*-bromophenylurea and chloroacetic acid. The identity of the two compounds were established through superimposable ir curve, identical R_f value by tlc and undepressed m m.p.

Experimental

2-Phenylimino-4-oxazolidone (Ia): Phenyl urea (0.05 mol) was refluxed with chloroacetic acid (0.05 mol) in presence of sodium acetate (3.5 g) in absolute ethanol (25 ml) on a boiling water bath for 20 h. The reaction mixture was then poured into cold water and the precipitate washed with hot water. It was crystallised from rectified spirit to yield the product (80%), m.p. 207° (Found: N, 15.70. C₉H₈O₂N₂ requires N, 15.90%).

2-(*p*-Acetoxymercuriphenyl) imino-4-oxazolidone (IIa): 2-Phenylimino-4-oxazolidone (0.01 mol) in acetic acid-ethanol (1 : 1, 10 ml) was treated with a solution of mercuric acetate (0.01 mol) in acetic

NOTES

TABLE 1—PHYSICAL AND PESTICIDAL DATA OF VARIOUS 2-ARYLIMINO-4-OXAZOLIDONES (I)* AND THEIR ACETOXYMERCURI DERIVATIVES (II)*

Sl. no.	R'	Oxazolidones (I)*					Hg Derivatives (II)*				
		M.p. °C	N% Found/ (Calcd.)	Activity			M.p. °C	Hg % Found/ (Calcd.)	Activity		
				Fungicidal ^a	Bactericidal ^b				Fungicidal ^a	Bactericidal ^b	
			<i>P. oryzae</i>	<i>E. coli</i>	<i>S. aureus</i>				<i>P. oryzae</i>	<i>E. coli</i>	<i>S. aureus</i>
R = H											
1.	C ₆ H ₅	207	15.70 (15.90)	5.0	-	-	242	45.98 (46.15)	3.0	+	+
2.	<i>o</i> -Cl.C ₆ H ₄	220	13.12 (13.30)	3.2	+	+	>250	42.60 (42.76)	1.5	+	+
3.	<i>m</i> -Cl.C ₆ H ₄	185	13.10 (13.30)	2.5	+	+	195 _a	42.55 (42.76)	1.5	+	+
4.	<i>p</i> -Cl.C ₆ H ₄	240	13.09 (13.30)	2.5	+	+	>250	42.62 (42.76)	1.5	+	+
5.	<i>p</i> -Br.C ₆ H ₄	>250	10.75 (10.98)	3.5	+	+	>250	38.82 (39.05)	2.2	-	+
6.	<i>o</i> -CH ₃ O.C ₆ H ₄	163	13.35 (13.59)	4.5	-	-	197	43.03 (43.17)	2.5	-	+
7.	<i>m</i> -CH ₃ O.C ₆ H ₄	141	13.40 (13.59)	4.0	-	-	185	43.05 (43.17)	2.8	-	+
8.	<i>p</i> -CH ₃ O.C ₆ H ₄	211	13.37 (13.59)	4.5	-	-	>250	43.00 (43.17)	3.0	-	+
9.	<i>o</i> -CH ₃ .C ₆ H ₄	235	14.51 (14.73)	5.5	+	-	>250	44.58 (44.71)	3.5	+	+
10.	<i>m</i> -CH ₃ .C ₆ H ₄	210	14.53 (14.73)	5.0	+	+	238	44.49 (44.71)	3.5	+	+
11.	<i>p</i> -CH ₃ .C ₆ H ₄	242	14.56 (14.73)	5.0	-	-	>250	44.56 (44.71)	3.0	+	+
R = CH ₃											
12.	C ₆ H ₅	223	14.51 (14.71)	6.5	-	-	>250	44.54 (44.71)	4.0	+	+
13.	<i>o</i> -Cl.C ₆ H ₄	225	12.25 (12.47)	4.0	-	+	>250	41.35 (41.52)	2.5	+	+
14.	<i>m</i> -Cl.C ₆ H ₄	216 _a	12.23 (12.47)	4.0	+	+	>250	41.40 (41.52)	2.5	+	+
15.	<i>p</i> -Cl.C ₆ H ₄	185	12.26 (12.47)	3.5	+	+	232	41.42 (41.52)	2.5	+	+
16.	<i>p</i> -Br.C ₆ H ₄	>250	10.19 (10.40)	4.4	+	+	>250	37.85 (38.02)	3.0	+	-
17.	<i>o</i> -CH ₃ O.C ₆ H ₄	190	12.48 (12.72)	4.8	-	-	201	41.75 (41.91)	3.5	-	-
18.	<i>m</i> -CH ₃ O.C ₆ H ₄	160	12.50 (12.72)	5.0	-	-	195 _a	41.80 (41.91)	4.5	+	+
19.	<i>p</i> -CH ₃ O.C ₆ H ₄	>250	12.51 (12.72)	5.2	-	+	>250	41.78 (41.91)	3.2	+	+
20.	<i>o</i> -CH ₃ .C ₆ H ₄	223	13.51 (13.72)	5.5	-	-	>250	43.25 (43.36)	3.5	-	-
21.	<i>m</i> -CH ₃ .C ₆ H ₄	195	13.50 (13.72)	5.0	-	-	230	43.27 (43.36)	3.5	+	+
22.	<i>p</i> -CH ₃ .C ₆ H ₄	246	13.48 (13.72)	6.0	-	-	>250	43.23 (43.36)	4.0	-	-

* Yield 60-80%, m.sp. uncorrected, satisfactory elemental analyses.

a - ppm for 50% spore germination.

b - At 100 ppm.

+ Active.

- Inactive.

acid (1N, 20 ml). The mixture was stirred well and kept overnight at room temperature. The resulting precipitate was filtered, washed with hot water and then with acetic acid-ethanol solution to yield the product (70%), m.p. 242° (Found : Hg, 45.98. C₁₁H₁₀O₄N₂Hg requires Hg, 46.15%).

Fungicidal activity: The compounds were screened for their fungicidal activity against *Pyricularia oryzae* (CaV) by the method of Montgomery and Moore⁸, and the results are given in Table 1. The results may be generalised as follows :

- (i) Almost all the compounds showed promising antifungal activity.
- (ii) Presence of halogen, especially chloride on the *N*-phenyl ring augments the antifungal activity remarkably.
- (iii) The compounds with R=H are more active than those with R=CH₃.
- (iv) Acetoxymercuri derivatives, **IIa** and **IIb** are in general about two times more active than

the corresponding non-mercurated oxazolidinones (Ia and Ib).

Bactericidal activity: The bactericidal activity of synthesised compounds, both mercurated and non-mercurated ones have been assayed against two common pathogenic bacteria, *E. coli* and *S. aureus*, separately by Rideal-Walker serial drop dilution method⁹. The results are given in Table I. Both the bacteria are equally sensitive towards the compounds Ia and Ib at 100 ppm level.

Acknowledgement

The authors are grateful to the B.S.I.R., Government of Orissa for financial assistance. One of the authors (S.C.S.) is grateful to the U.G.C., New Delhi for the award of a Teacher Fellowship.

References

1. J. W. CORNFORTH, "Heterocyclic Compounds", John Wiley, New York, 1956, Vol. 5.
2. I. D. DRUTTA and C. H. BUDEANU, *Chem. Abstr.*, 1973, 79, 137098.
3. R. S. VERMA, *J. Prakt. Chem.*, 1973, 315, 350.
4. R. B. FUGITT and L. C. MARTINELLI, *J. Pharm. Sci.*, 1973, 62, 613 (*Chem. Abstr.*, 1973, 79, 5321).
5. R. M. SILVERSTEIN, G. C. BASSLER and T. C. MORRILL, "Spectroscopic Identification of Organic Compounds", John Wiley, New York, 1974, p. 107.
6. M. K. ROUT and G. N. MAHAPATRA, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1955, 77, 2427.
7. G. N. MAHAPATRA and M. K. ROUT, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1955, 32, 715.
8. H. B. S. MONTGOMERY and M. H. MOORE, *J. Pomol. Hort. Sci.*, 1938, 15, 253.
9. S. RIDEAL and J. F. A. WALKER, *J. R. Sanit. Inst. London*, 1903, 24, 424.

Studies on 4-Thiazolidinones as Antibacterial Agents

S. J. SHAH, S. R. SHAH, N. C. DESAI and K. A. THAKER

University Department of Chemistry, Bhavnagar University, Bhavnagar-364 002

Manuscript received 30 January 1984, accepted 26 May 1984

PHENYLACETIC acid have been known to be active as bactericidal and fungicidal agent. Thiazolidinone derivatives are well known biological active compounds¹⁻⁶. Several substituted thiazolidinones were found to possess anaesthetic, anticonvulsant and sedative properties^{7,8}. Besides, compounds having N—C—S grouping have antitubercular⁹, antiradiation¹⁰, hematocidal¹¹ and antibacterial¹² activities. In view of the varied physiological activities of thiazolidinone derivatives several thiazolidinone derivatives have been prepared (II) by the cycloaddition of thioglycolic and thiomalic acid with different hydrazones (Schiff's base).

where R' = H and
R' = -CH₂.COOH

Experimental

Phenylacetylhydrazines: These were prepared by the reported method¹³.

Hydrazones (I): A mixture of phenylacetylhydrazine and aromatic aldehyde (0.01 mol each) in ethanol (30 ml) and piperidine (3-4 drops) was refluxed on water bath for 1 h. The reaction mixture was cooled, the separated solid was filtered and the product (I) recrystallised from ethanol. Melting points, yield and antibacterial activity of (I) are given in Table 1.

TABLE 1 - HYDRAZONES (I)

Sl. no.	R	M.p. °C	Antibacterial activity <i>E. coli</i> <i>S. aureus</i>	
1.	-C ₆ H ₅	148	-	-
2.	-2.OH.C ₆ H ₄ '	187	-	+
3.	-4.OCH ₃ .C ₆ H ₄	166	+	+
4.	-5.Br.2.OH.C ₆ H ₄	198	+	++
5.	-4.NO ₂ .C ₆ H ₄	197	-	-
6.	-3-NO ₂ .C ₆ H ₄	183	-	-
7.	-4.Cl.C ₆ H ₄	153	-	+
8.	-3,4-CH ₃ (O) ₂ .C ₆ H ₄	209	-	+
9.	-4.OH.3.OCH ₃ .C ₆ H ₄	135	+	+
10.	-3,4-di(OCH ₃) ₂ .C ₆ H ₄	168	+	+
11.	-4.OH.C ₆ H ₄	204	-	-
12.	-4.CH ₃ .C ₆ H ₄	137	-	-

C, H, N analyses within ±0.5% theoretical values.
Yield 65 - 75%.

+ = Zone dia. <20 mm.

++ = Zone dia. >20 mm.

- = No inhibitory zone.

4-Thiazolidinone (II): Method A. A mixture of appropriate hydrazone (I) (0.01 mol) and thioglycolic acid (0.015 mol) in dry benzene (30 ml) was refluxed for 8 h. Excess solvent and thioglycolic acid was removed under vacuum. The residue was washed thoroughly with NaHCO₃ solution and water, dried, and the product (II) crystallised from ethanol (95%).

Method B. A mixture of hydrazone (I) and thiomalic acid (0.01 mol each) was condensed in presence of anhydrous zinc chloride (0.5 g) at 160° for 2 h. The temperature was raised to 180° for 30 min, and the product dissolved in sodium bicarbonate (4 N) solution and filtered. The filtrate was